

1 **High Concordance in Plasma and CSF HIV-1 Drug Resistance Mutations Despite High**
2 **Cases of CSF Viral Escape in Individuals with HIV-Associated Cryptococcal Meningitis**
3 **in Botswana**

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18 ABSTRACT

19 **Objectives:** We compared the patterns of HIV-1 drug resistance mutations between the CSF
20 and plasma of individuals with HIV-associated cryptococcal meningitis.

21 **Methods:** This is a cross-sectional study of archived CSF and plasma samples collected from
22 ART-exposed participants recruited in the phase-3 Ambisome therapy Induction Optimisation
23 randomised controlled trial (ISRCTN72509687) conducted in Botswana between 2018-2021.
24 HIV-1 reverse transcriptase and protease genes were genotyped using next-generation
25 sequencing and HIV-1 drug resistance mutations were compared between the CSF and plasma
26 compartments stratified by thresholds of $\geq 20\%$ and $< 20\%$.

27 **Results:** Overall, 66.7% (16/24) of participants had at least one HIV-1 drug resistance mutation
28 in the CSF and/or plasma. A total of 15/22 (68.2%) participants had HIV-1 drug resistance
29 mutations at $\geq 20\%$ threshold in the plasma and of those, 11 (73.3%) had been on ART longer
30 than 6 months. HIV-1 drug resistance mutations were highly concordant between the CSF and
31 plasma at $\geq 20\%$ threshold despite a substantial number of individuals experiencing CSF viral
32 escape and with only 54.5% with CSF white blood cell count ≥ 20 cells/mm³. Minority HIV-1
33 drug resistance mutations were detected in 20.8% (5/24) of participants. There were no
34 mutations in the CSF that were not detected in the plasma.

35 **Conclusion:** There was high concordance in HIV-1 drug resistance mutations in the CSF and
36 plasma suggesting inter-compartmental mixing and possibly a lack of compartmentalisation.
37 Some individuals harboured minority HIV-1 drug resistance mutations demonstrating the need
38 to employ more sensitive genotyping methods such as next-generation sequencing for the
39 detection of low-abundance mutations.

40 INTRODUCTION

41 During the early course of infection, HIV-1 may enter the CNS by the migration of infected
42 CD4⁺ T-cells across the blood-brain barrier. ¹ Once in the CNS, the virus can infect and adapt

43 to cells that express low densities of CD4 (macrophages and microglial) leading to the
44 evolution of compartmentalised HIV-1 variants in the CNS. ² Compartmentalisation may also
45 arise due to limited penetration of some antiretroviral drugs into the CNS through the blood-
46 brain barrier and ART interruptions. ^{3,4} The accumulated HIV-1 drug resistance mutations may
47 persist for longer periods in the CNS leading to poor response to ART in the future. ^{1,5}
48 Despite the widespread access to ART, poor ART adherence and late presentation to care
49 remain the key challenges to ending HIV-associated opportunistic infections such as
50 cryptococcal meningitis. ⁶ While people with cryptococcal meningitis can present with HIV-1
51 drug resistance mutations, compartmentalisation of these mutations between the CSF and
52 plasma requires further investigation. This study compares HIV-1 drug resistance mutations
53 derived from the CSF and plasma of unsuppressed, mostly ART-exposed individuals with HIV-
54 associated cryptococcal meningitis in Botswana.

55 **METHODS**

56 **Study Population**

57 This was a cross-sectional study of archived CSF and plasma samples from participants
58 enrolled in the Botswana site as part of the phase-3 Ambisome Therapy Induction Optimisation
59 randomised controlled trial conducted between 2018 and 2021. Briefly, the trial compared
60 induction therapy of a single, high-dose of liposomal amphotericin B given alongside 14 days
61 of flucytosine and fluconazole with the World Health Organisation recommended first-line
62 regimen, which was a one-week amphotericin B deoxycholate with flucytosine followed by
63 one-week of fluconazole. Eighty-four participants were recruited in the Botswana site, with 46
64 being ART-naïve and 38 ART-exposed participants, however, we utilised samples from ART-
65 exposed participants only. From the 38 ART-exposed participants, 28 and 36 participants had
66 available CSF and plasma samples, respectively, collected on day 1 of the trial and 27 had
67 CSF/plasma paired samples. The study was approved by the University of Botswana

68 Institutional Review Board and the Health Research and Development Council at the Botswana
69 Ministry of Health (HPDME 13/18/1) and all participants explicitly consented to future use of
70 their samples.

71 **Laboratory Investigations**

72 HIV-1 viral load and CSF viral escape results which were previously reported were used in this
73 analysis.⁷ HIV-1 RNA was extracted from 140 µl of plasma and cell-free CSF using the
74 QIAamp viral RNA mini kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). Complementary DNA strand from
75 protease and reverse transcriptase of HIV-1 *pol* was amplified as previously described.⁸ The
76 purified amplicons were used for next-generation sequencing on Illumina Miseq (Illumina
77 K.K., Tokyo, Japan). The sequence reads obtained were analyzed using PAseq
78 (<https://paseq.org/>) and HyDRA Web (<http://hydra.canada.ca>).

79 HIV-1 drug resistance mutations were considered high frequency if detected at $\geq 20\%$ allele
80 frequency while low-frequency mutations were defined as those occurring between 5% and
81 20% allele frequency. HIV-1 drug resistance mutations detected were reported using the
82 Stanford HIV drug resistance database (<http://hivdb.stanford.edu>). The CSF/plasma consensus
83 sequences obtained were included in the maximum-likelihood phylogeny inferred in IQ-TREE
84 2 under the General Time Reversible model of nucleotide substitution and a total of 1000
85 bootstrap replicates.⁹ Sequences were subtyped using REGA subtyping tool version 3.¹⁰

86 **RESULTS**

87 **Participants Characteristics**

88 Baseline demographics and clinical characteristics of the 24 ART-exposed participants with
89 successful genotyping results are shown in Supplementary Table 1. The median age was 39.5
90 years (IQR: 34.0-44.8 years) and two-thirds of the participants were male. Most participants
91 (41.7%) were on Tenofovir, Lamivudine and Efavirenz. The median duration on ART was 62.5
92 months (IQR: 1.5-100 months). The median CD4+ T-cell count at enrolment was 30 cells/mm³

93 (IQR: 10.8-60.0 cells/mm³) while median CSF and plasma HIV-1 viral load were 4.4 (3.6-5.2)
94 log₁₀ copies/ml and 4.8 (3.9-5.3) log₁₀ copies/ml, respectively.

95 **HIV-1 Drug Resistance Mutations in the CSF and Plasma**

96 Of the 24 participants with successful genotyping results; 11 were CSF/plasma pairs, 11 were
97 unpaired plasma and 2 were unpaired CSF. Maximum-likelihood phylogenetic analysis
98 revealed a 100% bootstrap value for all the pairs confirming patient-level viral sequence
99 uniqueness (Figure 1A). A total of 15/22 (68.2%) participants had HIV-1 drug resistance
100 mutations at ≥20% threshold in the plasma and of those, 11 (73.3%) had been on ART longer
101 than 6 months (Table 1). NRTI and NNRTI-associated mutations were found in 11/15 (73.3%)
102 and 13/15 (86.7%) participants, respectively while PI-associated mutations were detected in
103 1/15 (6.7%) participants. Overall, 5/24 (20.8%) participants harboured minority HIV-1 drug
104 resistance mutations in the CSF or plasma. Out of 11 participants with paired CSF/plasma
105 samples, 5 (45.5%) had CSF viral escape while 7/11 (63.6%) had pleocytosis (CSF white blood
106 cell count ≥10 cells/mm³ as previously described).¹ There were 8/11 participants with paired
107 samples harbouring HIV-1 drug resistance mutations in the CSF and/or plasma, of those, 5
108 (62.5%) experienced pleocytosis and 4 (50.0%) had CSF viral escape while 4 (50.0%) were
109 mutually inclusive of both variables. There were 2/11 (18.2%) participants with discordant
110 HIV-1 drug resistance mutations, however, there were no mutations in CSF that were not
111 present in plasma, but two participants had additional mutations in the plasma.

112 The most prevalent NNRTI-associated mutations in the plasma and CSF were V106M and
113 Y181C which cause high-level resistance to nevirapine and efavirenz, respectively (Figure 1B).
114 K65R and M184V were the most prevalent NRTI mutations in the plasma both occurring in
115 31.8% (7/22) of participants while K65R also predominated in the CSF with a prevalence of
116 30.8% (4/13) (Figure 1C).

117 **DISCUSSION**

118 We report a high prevalence (66.7%) of HIV-1 drug resistance mutations in ART-exposed
119 individuals with HIV-associated cryptococcal meningitis which may contribute to the
120 transmission of these mutations. The most predominant mutations were M184V and K65R
121 indicating long-term exposure and poor adherence to the tenofovir plus lamivudine or
122 Emtricitabine regimen. Although these individuals can safely continue tenofovir, lamivudine
123 and dolutegravir or switch to zidovudine, lamivudine and dolutegravir,¹¹ the long-term
124 efficacy of these regimens in patients harbouring HIV-1 with these mutations requires further
125 investigations. Our results suggest that both poor adherence to ART and the development of
126 HIV-1 drug resistance mutations contribute to HIV disease progression and the development
127 of opportunistic infections like cryptococcal meningitis.

128 Our study also revealed a high concordance in the CSF and plasma HIV-1 drug resistance
129 mutations harboured by these individuals and there were no mutations in the CSF that were not
130 detected in the plasma. Furthermore, approximately half of the participants with paired samples
131 harbouring drug resistance mutations experienced pleocytosis and CSF viral escape. These
132 results corroborate previous research findings demonstrating minimal HIV-1
133 compartmentalisation and intercompartmental mixing of the viral populations.¹² This also
134 provides additional evidence that the high influx of HIV-1 infected CD4+ T-cells into the CNS
135 accounts for the equilibration of these viruses in the two compartments and possibly a lack of
136 independent evolution and replication of the virus in the CNS.^{1,13} These findings may provide
137 reassurance to ART prescribers in that, in this cohort, a switch in the patient's ART regimen
138 based on the drug resistance profile from plasma would still be effective in the CSF, unlike in
139 scenarios where there are additional mutations in the CSF. We further noted two participants
140 with additional HIV-1 drug resistance mutations in the plasma suggesting possible selective
141 drug pressure in the plasma as opposed to the CSF.¹⁴

142 When comparing the HIV-1 drug resistance mutations in the CSF and plasma using next-
143 generation sequencing we found 20.8% of the participants harbouring HIV-1 drug resistance
144 minority variants. This shows that the use of next-generation sequencing is critical in detecting
145 low abundance mutations that may have an impact on treatment outcomes and potentially drive
146 viral escape. Although conventional next-generation sequencing has limitations of decreasing
147 accurate sampling of the original viral population and high error rates affecting the downstream
148 analysis and interpretation, conventional next generation-sequencing is still widely used even
149 in studies with public health impact, and ¹⁵ it outperforms Sanger sequencing in detecting
150 mutations at <20% threshold. ¹⁶ To mitigate these problems, we recommend the use of unique
151 primer IDs which will increase the sensitivity for the detection of minor variants. ^{17,18} Another
152 limitation of this study is that in our sequencing approach, we did not include the HIV-1
153 Integrase gene, however, studies show that the prevalence of pre-treatment Integrase inhibitors
154 resistance is relatively low since they have been recently introduced. ¹⁹ Lastly, our study had a
155 modest sample size utilising all available samples but was conducted in the context of a well-
156 designed clinical trial and high rates of virologic suppression in Botswana. We, therefore,
157 recommend further studies with larger sample sizes to profile and especially evaluate the
158 impact of HIV-1 drug resistance mutations in the CSF.

159 In summary, the high prevalence of HIV-1 drug resistance mutations shows the need to enhance
160 ART adherence and monitor HIV-1 viral load in individuals on ART to control the transmission
161 of HIV-1 drug resistance mutations and the development of opportunistic infections. The
162 presence of highly concordant HIV-1 drug resistance mutations between the CSF and plasma
163 could indicate inter-compartmental mixing and lack of HIV compartmentalisation in the CNS
164 in individuals with HIV-associated cryptococcal meningitis.

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189 TSH was a recipient of an investigator award to his institution from Gilead Sciences, speaker
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192 **Author Contributions**

193 N.K., R.M., I.K., D.S.L., M.M., T.S.H., J.N.J. and S.M., S.G conceived and designed the study;
194 K.L and T.B.L collected and prepared the study samples; N.K performed the laboratory
195 experiments; N.K., W.T.C., S.M and S.G conducted formal analysis and prepared the original
196 manuscript draft; I.K., S.G. and S.M supervised the research; S.M., R.M. and S.G acquired
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198 S.M and S.G participated in manuscript editing and approved the final version; All authors read
199 and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

200 **Data Availability**

201 Data is contained within the article and the relevant sequences are available on GenBank under
202 accession numbers ON773625 to ON773655.

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Table 1: HIV drug resistance mutations in the CSF and Plasma at $\geq 20\%$ and $< 20\%$ Threshold in people with HIV-associated cryptococcal meningitis in Botswana

ID	ART regimen	Months on ART (days)	HIV-1 viral load (\log_{10} copies/ml)				HIV-1 Drug Resistance Mutations ($\geq 20\%$ frequency)			HIV-1 Drug Resistance Mutations ($< 20\%$ frequency)	
			CSF	PLASMA	CSF WBC (cells/mm ³)	CSF Viral Escape	CSF	PLASMA	CSF	PLASMA	
1	TDF/3TC/EFV	74 (2259)	165508	390036	2	No	None	None	None	None	
2	TDF/3TC/EFV	8 (260)	414	79899	2	No	N/A	K65R, Y115F, E138A, G190E	N/A	None	
3	TDF/3TC/EFV	66 (2027)	N/A	9534	390	N/A	N/A	M184V, D67N, K103N, V106M, E138A	N/A	A62V, K65R	
4	TDF/3TC/EFV	64 (1964)	322572	422256	455	No	None	None	None	None	
5	TDF/3TC/DTG	0 (7)	4730	1143	62	Yes	None	Y188H	None	None	
6	TDF//3TC/EFV	34 (1063)	362670	49275	10	Yes	K65R, Y115F, T69G, A98G, Y181C, Y188H, G190A	L90M, K65R, Y115F, T69G, A98G, Y181C, Y188H, G190A	L90M, T69del	T69del, K101EQ	
7	TDF/3TC/LPV/r	112 (3420)	1129270	119019	130	Yes	None	None	None	None	
8	AZT/3TC/NVP	139 (4231)	N/A	102408	7	N/A	N/A	E138Q	N/A	None	
9	TDF/3TC/DTG	0 (16)	670	120	8	Yes	None	N/A	K65R, Y115F, A98G, E138A, G190A, Y188H, L90M, D67G, E138AGQ, G190AE, Y181C	N/A	
10	TDF/3TC/EFV	0 (10)	6356	1566	80	Yes	N/A	M184V, Y188L	N/A	K65R, Y115F, V106M	
11	Unknown	41 (1250)	43354	258912	2	No	E138A	E138A	None	None	
12	AZT/3TC/EFV	160 (4875)	9432	66285	2	No	N/A	M184V, K103N, P225H	N/A	None	
13	TDF/3TC/DTG	0 (5)	N/A	40470	208	N/A	N/A	None	N/A	None	
14	DTG/Other	67 (2061)	50812	66576	10	No	M184V	M184V	None	None	
15	TDF/3TC/EFV	72 (2213)	26088	184959	2	No	A62V, K65R, D67G, V75I, K219E, E138G, G190E, H221Y	A62V, K65R, D67G, V75I, K219E, E138G, G190E, H221Y	None	None	
16	TDF/3TC/DTG	2 (77)	38864	3393	85	Yes	E138A	E138A	None	None	
17	ABC/3TC/DTG	3 (107)	N/A	2130	13	N/A	N/A	M184I, A98G	N/A	None	
18	TDF/3TC/EFV	109 (3338)	13200792	2019123	145	Yes	K65R, Y115F, M184V, V106M, Y188L	K65R, Y115F, M184V, V106M, Y188L	None	None	
19	TDF/3TC/DTG	0 (14)	2142	24492	5	No	None	None	None	None	
20	TDF/3TC/DTG	97 (2955)	4324	135471	2	No	N/A	K65R, M184V	N/A	None	
21	TDF/3TC/EFV	138 (4202)	N/A	586368	2	N/A	N/A	None	N/A	None	
22	TDF/3TC/EFV	131 (3990)	N/A	43704	5	N/A	N/A	D67N, T69D, K70R, M184V, K219E, V106M, Y181C, G190A	N/A	V108I	
23	unknown	61 (1861)	N/A	269532	5	N/A	N/A	None	N/A	None	
24	TDF/3TC/DTG	0 (6)	1142	3219	2	N/A	None	N/A	None	N/A	

ABC, Abacavir; *3TC*, Lamivudine; *ARV*, antiretroviral drug; *AZT*, Zidovudine; *DTG*, Dolutegravir; *EFV*, Efavirenz; *LPV/r*, Ritonavir-boosted Lopinavir; *N/A*, data not available; *None*, No major drug-resistance mutations; *TDF*, Tenofovir disoproxil fumarate.

A.

B.

C.

Figure 1: A. Maximum-likelihood phylogenetic tree of 35 *Pol* sequences and reference genome (HXB2). The sequences have been isolated from plasma (open circle) and CSF (closed circle). Bootstrap values above 90 are indicated with paired sequences having a bootstrap value of 100. B. Frequency of NNRTI-associated mutations in participants' CSF and plasma samples (both paired and unpaired). C. Frequency of NRTI-associated mutations in participants' CSF and plasma samples (both paired and unpaired).